

Short communication

***Agdistis falkovitshi* (Lep.: Pterophoridae: Agdistinae), a new record for the fauna of Iran**

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چکیده

ضمن بررسی نمونه‌های Microlepidoptera جمع‌آوری شده از منطقه گنده از توابع ساوجبلاغ استان البرز، نمونه‌ای بال‌پولک‌دار متعلق به جنس *Agdistis* Hübner از خانواده Pterophoridae و زیرخانواده Agdistinae با نام علمی *Agdistis falkovitshi* Zagulajev, 1986 مورد شناسایی قرار گرفت. این گونه که تاکنون از ازبکستان، ترکمنستان، قزاقستان و مغولستان گزارش شده است، برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود و به این ترتیب تعداد گونه‌های این جنس در ایران به ۱۷ عدد می‌رسد.

The members of the genus *Agdistis* Hübner with estimated 108 species worldwide, occur in Palaearctic region, Africa, North America, and South Asia (Gielis, 2003, 2008, 2011; Altermatt, 2008; Ustjuzhanin & Kovtunovich, 2011). A total of 16 species of this genus have been previously reported from Iran (Staudinger & Rebel, 1901; Bigot, 1968; Sutter, 1991; Arenberger, 1990, 1995, 2002; Alipanah & Ustjuzhanin, 2006). During the study of the microlepidoptera species of Alborz province, a female specimen was collected and determined as *Agdistis falkovitshi* Zagulajev, 1986. The locality data of this specimen is as follows: 1 ♀, Alborz province: Sāvōjbolāgh, Gatehdeh, N 36°10'39", E 51°02'20.9", 2260 m., 31.vii.–01.viii.2007, leg. Zahiri, Ālipanāh & Falsafi.

This species, which is already reported from Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan and Mongolia (Arenberger, 1995; Gielis, 2003), differs from other related species in having a short denticle-like process at

the base of the median distal cleft of bifurcated eighth abdominal sternite of the male. Wingspan 21 mm (in the examined specimen), slightly larger than those of Arenberger (1995); ground color of forewing grey-brown with clear spots in costal margin; cone-shaped frons; the thin uncus in male genitalia shorter than length of each branch of bifurcated eighth sternite; aedeagus with some bending in its length; antrum in female genitalia strongly sclerotized and obliquely curved; ostium concave; apophyses anteriores stub-like, female with bifurcated posterior margin of eighth abdominal sternite (Arenberger, 1995).

This is the first record of this species from Iran and thereby, the total number of the reported species of *Agdistis* in Iran increases to 17 species.

The specimen is deposited at the Lepidoptera collection of the Hayk Mirzayans Insect Museum, Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection, Tehran, Iran.

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Received: 26 September 2012

Accepted: 23 January 2013